

**AWARENESS LEVEL OF LEARNERS ABOUT OPEN AND DISTANCE
LEARNING (ODL) FOR STUDY OF INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE
SYSTEM**

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Abstract

Awareness is the first step towards participation in any educational programme. In the context of Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS), awareness about Open and Distance Learning (ODL) becomes particularly important, as it provides opportunities for learners to access, study, and preserve traditional knowledge beyond the boundaries of conventional classrooms. Learners need to be aware not only of the nature and functioning of ODL but also of its potential for learning indigenous traditions, practices, cultural heritage, and local knowledge systems. The study examines the level of awareness among learners regarding the use of ODL for the study of Indigenous Knowledge Systems. The findings reveal that the majority of learners are familiar with the ODL mode of education and recognize its usefulness in accessing educational resources related to indigenous knowledge. However, awareness varies across different aspects of ODL and many learners are not fully informed about the specific learning opportunities, resources, and programmes available for the study of Indigenous Knowledge Systems. The study further indicates that learners develop a deeper understanding of ODL after actively engaging with the system. Self-Learning Materials (SLMs) continue to play a vital role in supporting learning in ODL, particularly by organizing indigenous knowledge content into structured units and blocks that facilitate independent study. The study highlights the need for greater dissemination of information and learner support so that ODL can serve as an effective platform for the preservation, transmission, and study of Indigenous Knowledge Systems.

Key Words: Awareness, Learners, Open and Distance Learning (ODL), Indigenous Knowledge System, Self-Learning Materials (SLMs), Traditional Knowledge.

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Introduction

ODL system of education is based on Web Enabled Academic Support (WEAS) and Nithya, et.al. (2016) have emphasised that mobile learning (M-Learning) can be used as an educative tool to improve the socio-economic conditions of our vast rural population and more effective tools. Community Radio play important role in boosting awareness level and enhancing knowledge about the methods of purifying water, weaning food, immunization and other government programmes (Sharma and Kashyap, 2016). Many professionals are using ICT for educational purpose (Mishra and Mishra, 2016).

Learning gives creativity, creativity leads to thinking, thinking provides knowledge, and knowledge makes you great. Teaching is a very noble profession that shapes the character, calibre, and future of an individual. It the people remember me as a good teacher that will be the biggest honour for me (APJ Abdul Kalam).

We know that there are three components of behaviour- Knowledge, Attitude and Skill. There are a number of theories seeking to model the process whereby attitudes might be translated into behaviours. One of the most commonly used and accessible of these is Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), which is formed on the basic premise that attitudes are significantly correlated to behavioural

intentions, which in turn are the proximal determinants of behaviour.

Any student decides to undertake or enrol in a specific program or curriculum only after acquiring adequate knowledge and awareness regarding it. The same principle applies to the study of Indigenous Knowledge Systems. The Open and Distance Learning (ODL) mode creates an opportunity for students to study local knowledge, traditions, culture, folk technologies, environmental knowledge, and the experiential wisdom of indigenous communities. Therefore, the level of student awareness is a crucial factor when studying Indigenous Knowledge Systems through ODL. Ryan and Gross (1943) noted that several stages are involved in the adoption of any new concept or innovation. They identified awareness, interest, evaluation, trial adoption, and satisfaction as the key steps in this process.

Students typically learn about ODL and curricula related to Indigenous Knowledge Systems through social interactions, peer groups, educational institutions, mass media, or other sources of information. It is based on this information that they make the decision to study Indigenous Knowledge through ODL. Decision-making is a continuous process, comprising a coordination of activities across various stages. The North Central Rural Sociology Sub-committee on the

Diffusion of Farm Practices (1955) identified five distinct stages in this adoption process. These stages are awareness, interest, evaluation, trial application, and adoption.

At the awareness stage, a student learns about the opportunity to study Indigenous Knowledge Systems through ODL; however, they may not yet possess a comprehensive understanding of its curriculum, study materials, pedagogical methods, or potential utility. The student may know the name of the program but remains largely uninformed about its specific objectives and practical efficacy. It is only after acquiring further information about the program that a sense of interest begins to emerge within them.

At the interest stage, the student seeks to gather more information regarding the opportunity to study Indigenous Knowledge through ODL, the course content, and its potential benefits. They attempt to understand how this educational approach can facilitate the preservation, documentation, and intergenerational transmission of traditional knowledge. Following this stage, the student begins to evaluate the practical effectiveness of the program. During the evaluation phase, the student considers the advantages and limitations of studying Indigenous Knowledge through ODL, and assesses how effectively this approach might fulfil their educational needs and future aspirations.

Concurrently, they evaluate the extent to which participation in such a curriculum could foster the development of their knowledge and skills.

In the experimental phase, the student initially seeks to verify the efficacy of ODL by enrolling in a certificate, diploma, or short-term training program. Should they determine that this educational modality is well-suited to their needs and effective for the study of Indigenous Knowledge, they may then decide to enrol in higher-level courses or degree programs. Once satisfied with the ODL framework and its pedagogical processes, students advocate for the positive aspects of this method to others, thereby playing a pivotal role in promoting its significance for the study and preservation of Indigenous Knowledge Systems.

Literature Review

According to Singh (1965), the stages of adoption are dynamic and not static. The same five stages do not occur with all the adopters and all the practices. Some learners will take admission in ODL because of their need of it without complete awareness. When learner feel need of any programme which is not in regular mode then he/she will get awareness about the ODL. Thus, sequence is not always the same, and some stage appears more than once.

Knowledge comes after awareness of the programme or any idea. Knowledge occurs when an individual or other decision-

making unit is exposed to an innovation's existence and gains some understanding of how it functions. Knowledge seeking is initiated by an individual and is greatly influenced by one's predispositions. Exposure is selective and generally an individual tends to expose to those ideas which are consistent with one's existing attitudes and beliefs and avoids those which are in conflict with them. A need can motivate learner to seek information about an ODL and the knowledge of a ODL may develop the need (Ray, 2011).

At present scenario of education system in the world especially after the covid-19 pandemic, ODL has taken place in education in all the sectors such as technical, social, arts, and managerial field of education. Agarwal and Lakshmi (2020) have conducted study on "Assessing Entrepreneurial Skills and Awareness among Learners of Open Universities in India: A Study of BRAOU and UOU, with descriptive research methods and primary data to examine learners' ability to perform in business after completion of programme through ODL mode. Most of the ODL learners are positively agree that they are able to run any business based on programme completed from ODL institutes. But, some of the modification needs to be restructured to help build a skilled labour force that is able to meet the ever-changing demand in both local and global markets.

Objective

The research study is with the following objectives:

- To assess the level of awareness among learners regarding Open and Distance Learning (ODL) as a medium for the study
- To examine how far compatible the learning in preservation, and dissemination of Indigenous Knowledge Systems.

Methodology

A conceptual framework identifies the direct and indirect relationships that are present in understanding a research issue. In the conceptual framework we have explained relationship between variables. Conceptual framework for the study shows the path of research and establishing relationship among the study variables (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for awareness level study

After reviewing of literature, we can find out the various aspects of ODL mode of education and framed a conceptual framework and briefly discussed here. These aspects are related to knowledge level of the respondents, awareness about the ODL mode of education and their perception towards ODL. Awareness affects knowledge and the knowledge creates interest, the interest raises desire-ness, the desire-ness promotes to adopt the system of education, adoption changes the perception either positive or negative. The knowledge of, awareness about, and perception towards- ODL system, quality and delivery of SLM of ODL, Student support services, teaching/counselling methods and evaluation/assessment methods and other related components of ODL. All these components of conceptual framework will be linked with cost effectiveness and cost efficiency of ODL mode of education. As we have discussed above that respondent would be both from tradition system of education and ODL system of education and established all the possible relationship to find out the perception towards ODL as compared to the traditional education.

Data has been collected by google form and

Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS):
Concept and Significance

The Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) refers to a system of knowledge

developed by indigenous and local communities through their long-standing experiences, observations, beliefs, values, and ways of life. This knowledge is transmitted from generation to generation through oral traditions, social practices, agriculture, folk medicine, forest resource management, and various cultural activities. This knowledge system is intimately intertwined with human life, society, culture, and the natural environment. According to UNESCO, Indigenous Knowledge constitutes a body of knowledge, skills, and perspectives that local and indigenous communities have developed based on their long-term relationships and experiences with their environment (UNESCO, 2024). This knowledge is grounded in local realities and enriched through practical experience. Consequently, it holds particular significance in the fields of agriculture, healthcare, natural resource management, and environmental conservation (UNESCO LINKS, 2024).

Currently, the significance of the Indigenous Knowledge System is gaining increasing recognition in the contexts of sustainable development, biodiversity conservation, and climate change mitigation (IPBES, 2024). However, under the influence of modernization, urbanization, and cultural shifts, many elements of this knowledge system are at risk of being lost. Therefore, the preservation, documentation, and

intergenerational transmission of Indigenous Knowledge have become imperative. In this context, Open and Distance Learning (ODL) systems can play a pivotal role. Through ODL, it is possible to disseminate educational materials, research, and learning opportunities related to Indigenous Knowledge to a wider audience. As a result, the preservation and dissemination of this knowledge system can be accomplished more effectively.

Awareness Level of Learner about ODL Mode Education

Before discussion about the learner's awareness level and knowledge level or their perception towards the ODL we have describes what the components of behaviour are. Table 1 presents awareness level and knowledge level of learners about the ODL mode of education and its functions. It is very happy to note here that all of them were aware about the ODL but more than half of them (55.4%) were fully aware about the ODL system of education. They may be enrolled in the ODL any programme either degree or diploma. We have targeted respondent only those have either currently enrolled, or they have completed their any programme. That is why all are aware about the ODL. They have asked "what is the source of ODL information?" and all of them have given mixed response and many of them agreed that newspaper and

friend/relative/peer groups are major source of information about the ODL.

Table 1: Awareness and Use of ODL system of Education

1. Do you know ODL Mode of Education?	%
Aware	44.6
Fully Aware	55.4
Total	305
2. Have you completed any programme in ODL mode?	
No	42.0
Yes	58.0
Total	305
3. If yes, what programme have you completed?	
Diploma	36.7
Certificate	6.8
Degree	47.5
All the Above	9.0
Total	177
Knows nature of ODL mode	92.8

Table 2: Awareness level about the ODL and its components

ODL Components	Aware	Fully Aware	Not Aware
ODL Mode of Education	44.6	55.4	-
SLM Quality and delivery	47.2	36.6	16.2
Student Support Centre	49.3	40.9	9.7
ODL Counseling/Teaching	49.1	41.0	9.9
Evaluation and Assessment	52.2	39.7	8.1
Efficiency of ODL	47.5	39.4	13.1

We have further asked respondent "have you completed any programme from ODL" they have responded binary yes (58.0

%) and no (42 %). Table 1 Nine percent of them have completed degree, diploma and certificate. Close to half of them (47.5%) have completed degree followed by diploma (36.7%). A vast majority of them (92.8%) knows the nature of ODL mode i.e., blended mode of learning.

Freudian Psychology help to know us the conscious, preconscious, and unconscious awareness about the object. Each of these levels interferes and overlaps with Freud's ideas of the Id, Ego, and Superego. These three agencies are components of the personality development. Id is the basic instinct, what one is born with needs, happiness, desires, etc. Id is unaware of the external world and the passage of time, and it is the inherited part of the personality while ego is what I am or myself. The superego is governed by morals and societal compasses. Example of Id is that learner want to get certificate for that he/she is doing all the efforts until unless not get certificate. Learner perceived that it is not tough to get degree from ODL, but he has some fear about the cost and time and importance of degree/diploma/certificate, and final postpone the decision, it is the example of ego. Example for superego, if learner has chance to get degree from ODL institute without any problems by using favourism from the staff or other means, but learner feel that it would be Sin and would feel guilt and owing to this mindset, learner

will avoid ODL programme or not enrolled (Dahama and Bhatnagar, 2011). Thus, perception, awareness and change attitude are the result of id, ego and superego and all these three components influence personality development.

Table 2 clearly shows that almost all the learners were aware and fully aware about the ODL and its components. Interesting to note here that none of the respondents have responded that they were not aware about the ODL mode of education, many of them were not aware about all components of ODL mode of education. It indicates that fully awareness comes after using of the system of ODL. Self-Learning Materials (SLMs) are base of ODL. The course materials are significant inputs of learning in distance education system. Usually in the Indian context they are understood as print-based self-study materials. As a student of ODLS you have noticed that the study materials are classified into different areas of study in the form of Blocks and Units.

There are six components of ODL i.e., ODL Mode of Education; SLM Quality and delivery; Student Support Centre; ODL Counselling/Teaching; Evaluation and Assessment; and Efficiency of ODL. Awareness level of learners/respondents have discussed following sub-headings:

Table 3: Awareness Level of learners about the ODL System and Its components by Socio-economic Characteristics, 2023

S. No.	Items	ODL Mode of Education		SLM Quality and delivery			Student Support Centre			Total (N)
		A	FA	NA	A	FA	NA	A	FA	
1	Age (years)									
	0-32	50.0	50.0	18.6	56.7	24.7	7.4	62.0	30.6	98
	33-42	41.0	59.0	14.0	42.0	44.0	10.0	42.0	48.0	97
	43+	42.2	57.8	16.1	42.5	41.4	12.2	42.2	45.6	87
2	Marital status									
	Married	45.2	54.8	19.7	38.6	41.7	12.2	42.7	45.0	126
	Single	42.5	57.5	12.8	53.7	33.6	7.0	54.8	38.2	146
	Others	70.0	30.0	25.0	62.5	12.5	20.0	50.0	30.0	10
3	Place of Birth									
	Rural	41.4	58.6	15.0	49.7	35.3	12.7	45.2	42.0	153
	Urban	48.3	51.7	17.6	44.3	38.2	6.4	53.9	39.7	129
4	Education Level									
	Graduate	52.1	47.9	26.4	46.0	27.6	15.2	51.1	33.7	83
	Postgraduate	41.3	58.7	15.1	47.5	37.4	9.3	47.1	43.6	138
	PhD	41.2	58.8	3.4	48.3	48.3	3.0	51.5	45.5	61
5	Sex									
	Male	41.7	58.3	15.0	46.0	39.0	9.9	46.2	43.9	202
	Female	51.7	48.3	19.0	50.0	31.0	9.3	57.0	33.7	80
6	Religion									
	Hindu	29.7	70.3	11.8	38.2	50.0	5.4	45.9	48.6	36
	Other	46.6	53.4	16.8	48.4	34.8	10.3	49.8	39.8	246
7	Social Group									
	SC	29.6	70.4	12.5	50.0	37.5	7.4	51.9	40.7	26
	ST	47.1	52.9	14.3	42.9	42.9	23.5	41.2	35.3	14
	OBC	46.8	53.2	19.4	54.8	25.8	7.5	59.1	33.3	91
	Others	45.5	54.5	15.0	42.5	42.5	9.9	44.1	46.0	151
8	Employment status									
	Salaried	49.1	50.9	14.6	49.7	35.7	8.1	50.3	41.6	152
	Student	38.0	62.0	18.5	45.7	35.8	11.2	51.7	37.1	84
	others	41.7	58.3	17.4	41.3	41.3	12.5	41.7	45.8	46
	Total ()	44.6	55.4	16.2	47.2	36.6	9.7	49.3	40.9	282
	Total (N)	136	169	46	134	104	29	147	122	

Note- A-Aware, FA-Fully Aware, NA- Not Aware
Source: Primary 2023

Awareness about Self Learning Materials and its delivery

Respondents have asked about the awareness about each component of ODL in three scale such as fully aware, aware and not aware by their socio-economic background. Table 3 depicts that response about the Self Learning Materials (SLM) that most of them fully aware with increasing their ages. Age group of learner 33-42 years is fully aware about the SLM, and its delivery as compared to younger age group of the learners. Married male living in rural areas was more aware about the SLM and its delivery as compared to the rest of the learners. Postgraduate, Hindu and other

social groups were more aware about the SLM as compared to the higher educated learners who have either enrolled or have completed their degree or diploma under ODL mode. Salaried employees are fully aware about the SLM and its delivery but 8.7 percent of unemployed were not aware about the SLM.

Table 3 Contd.: Awareness Level of learners about the ODL System and Its components by Socio-economic Characteristics, 2023

S. No.	Items	ODL Counseling/ Teaching			Evaluation and Assessment			Efficiency of ODL			Total (N)
		NA	A	FA	NA	A	FA	NA	A	FA	
1	Age (years)										
	0-32	9.8	59.8	30.4	6.8	62.1	31.1	11.2	60.2	28.6	98
	33-42	9.2	43.9	46.9	8.8	46.1	45.1	15.5	38.1	46.4	97
	43+	10.8	42.2	47.0	8.9	47.8	43.3	12.6	43.7	43.7	87
2	Marital status										
	Married	13.6	41.6	44.8	13.6	43.9	42.4	16.7	38.1	45.2	126
	Single	7.4	53.4	39.2	3.9	57.4	38.7	11.0	52.7	36.3	146
	Others	0.0	80.0	20.0	0.0	87.5	12.5	0.0	90.0	10.0	10
3	Place of Birth										
	Rural	13.2	44.1	42.8	9.6	51.9	38.5	15.7	44.4	39.9	153
	Urban	6.1	55.0	38.9	6.5	52.5	41.0	10.1	51.2	38.8	129
4	Education Level										
	Graduate	14.8	55.6	29.6	13.3	48.9	37.8	16.9	51.8	31.3	83
	Postgraduate	8.8	48.9	42.3	8.6	54.3	37.1	13.8	44.9	41.3	138
	PhD	6.2	41.5	52.3	0.0	52.3	47.7	6.6	47.5	45.9	61
5	Sex										
	Male	9.3	49.0	41.7	7.1	50.5	42.4	11.9	47.0	41.1	202
	Female	11.4	49.4	39.2	10.6	56.5	32.9	16.3	48.8	35.0	80
6	Religion										
	Hindu	8.1	40.5	51.4	2.9	37.1	60.0	13.9	38.9	47.2	36
	Other	10.2	50.4	39.4	8.8	54.2	36.9	13.0	48.8	38.2	246
7	Social Group										
	SC	15.4	42.3	42.3	0.0	72.0	28.0	19.2	46.2	34.6	26
	ST	14.3	64.3	21.4	11.8	64.7	23.5	14.3	50.0	35.7	14
	OBC	14.0	50.0	36.0	10.9	53.3	35.9	11.0	49.5	39.6	91
	Others	6.4	48.4	45.2	7.5	47.2	45.3	13.2	46.4	40.4	151
8	Employment status										
	Salaried	6.0	54.3	39.7	9.4	51.3	39.4	6.6	55.9	37.5	152
	Student	15.1	51.2	33.7	5.7	56.3	37.9	21.4	40.5	38.1	84
	others	13.0	28.3	58.7	8.3	47.9	43.8	19.6	32.6	47.8	46
	Total ()	9.9	49.1	41.0	8.1	52.2	39.7	13.1	47.5	39.4	282
	Total (N)	28	139	116	24	154	117	37	134	111	305

It is not clear that why most of the learners are not aware about the SLM and its delivery although they are currently enrolled in any ODL programme or they have completed their any programme from the ODL. It indicates the lack of interest and lack of time to understand about the ODL and its functions. Just they completed their programme and forget what the ODL and they are have just heard about the ODL and enrolled and didn't bother about the ODL programme.

Aware about the Student Support Centre (SSC)

Awareness about the ODL is the first step of perceiving positively or negatively. As a student of ODL system you are aware of its different components. ODLS is understood as provision of learning opportunities and support by distance education institution to a distance learner through print-based materials, methods, activities, media and technologies for achievement of curricular aims and objectives. This statement leads us to identify six major elements of ODL System (ODLS), such as - Distance Learner, print based Study Materials, Media and Technology based instruction, Delivery system, Evaluation and Learner support system. The learner in ODLS occupies a key position. The ODL aims at facilitating learning and development of its students

who are located at a distance from a university/or a School (MDE413).

The learners' social, cultural, ethnic, geographical, economic and psychological backgrounds reveal multiplicity as well as compositeness. Unlike traditional education the target group of distance learners belongs to a varied age group, working class, housewives, economically scattered classes, remote geographical locations, varied caste groups and different nationalities. They are self-motivated learners.

Student Support Services are indispensable components of the ODL system (ODLS). It is important not because of its relation to the Distance Education theories, but it is a key for learners' successes and their persistence in the ODL system. It is a fact that in Distance Education, there is the geographical separation of teacher and learner (MDE413). Many of the respondents were not aware about the student support centre and its function in ODL. It indicates that they have completed their courses without proper understanding of distance education and its nature how it works. Male were more aware about the SSC and its functions and role in ODL as compared to their female counterparts. Married learners were more aware about the SSC as compared to the single and separated.

Aware about the Counselling in ODL

Counselling is the important component of ODL education. Counselling is not like classroom teaching, but it is remedial process of teaching in which learners and counselling interact each and discuss about the learning issues and challenges, solve the problems if any. Teaching is the process of facilitate the environment for learning, while counselling is the process of interacting for solution of the problems. In teaching, teacher is speaking, and learner is listening while in counselling learner is speaking and counsellor is listening to get their problems and understand their interest on the programme. Table 5.2 reveals that learner belongs age categories of 33-42 years were more aware about the counselling and its nature, while single and other marital status learners were more aware as compared to the married. It may be because single and separated have no family responsibilities and they have chance to refer library and maintain social networking. Due to media exposure and other means of information, urban people are more aware about the educational information as compared to rural people. PhD degree holder, male, Hindu, other social group and salaried people were more aware about the counselling of ODL as compared other categories of respondents. Some of them responded that counselling is not compulsory, but it is helping more for

writing assignment and preparation for term end examination. Counselling is a collaborative process through which individuals are helped to define goals, make decisions, and solve problems related to personal, social, educational and career concerns. In other words, counselling is a special category of human relationship that aims to help an individual to manage his/her problems (MDE-413).

Studying at a distance is both challenging and demanding. Helping distance learners to progress successfully through their studies is even more challenging. Counselling has a crucial role to play in this mode of teaching-learning. It intends to make the learners more effective by initiating the students into distance learning, guiding self-learning in the desirable direction, confirming positive learning and re-enforcing further learning, providing non-print interventions, promoting and sustaining motivation, developing studentship and learning skills, identifying person-specific problems and helping to overcome learning disabilities.

Aware about the Evaluation and Assessment Perception

Table 3 indicates that almost respond were aware and fully aware about the assessment in distance education. Some of them have not responded clearly or they could not understand the language of google form what is the objective of monkey

survey. ODL mode of education is based on two assessment level. Internal and external evaluation, assignment is internal evaluation and term end exam (TEE) and Project report (if any) are external evaluation. Learning portfolio is also used by some of the course coordinator. Online assessment also conducted for external evaluation. In assessing online learning, it is important to create a “mix” of assignments that cover the multiple dimensions of learning that online courses can employ. Traditional tests become a smaller part of the grade as we move towards encouraging student interaction on group projects and other activities (MDE-418).

An electronic portfolio, also known as an e-portfolio or digital portfolio, is a collection of electronic evidence assembled and managed by a user, usually on the web (also called web folio). An e-portfolio can be a web-based information management system that uses electronic media and services. The learner builds and maintains a digital repository of artifacts, which they can use to demonstrate competence and reflect on their learning. E-portfolios are both demonstrations of the user’s abilities and platforms for self-expression, and, if they are online, they can be maintained dynamically over time. Some e-portfolio applications permit varying degrees of audience access, so the same portfolio might be used for multiple purposes. E-portfolios,

like traditional portfolios, can facilitate students’ reflection on their own learning, leading to more awareness of learning strategies and needs. In this context, the use of an electronic portfolio helps us to achieve better learning outcomes. Table 3 further shows that there were 0-33 years of age, other marital status learners, urban, research (PhD) scholar, male and Hindu, SC and students were more aware about the evaluation and assessment of ODL.

Aware about the Efficiency of ODL

As we know that ODL is cost and time efficient mode of learning. Many of the learners were not aware about the importance of ODL. They know that working people can enrol in the ODL institute that is time efficient. Slightly more than one tenth (13.1%) of the learner were not aware about the efficiency of ODL system of education even though they are enrolled for getting certificate. Of them only enrolled because their peer groups have registered in ODL.

Table 4: Association between distance of study centre and frequency of visit to centre

Distance (KM)	How often you visit study centre (%)?						Chi-Square
	Never	Occasionally	Sometimes	Often	Always	Other	
<5	19.7	24.6	27.9	8.2	16.4	3.3	47.215**
6-10	17.3	44.2	26.9	5.8	5.8	0.0	
11-20	35.6	38.4	9.6	2.7	13.7	0.0	
21-50	34.3	20.0	45.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	
>50	23.8	26.2	35.7	1.2	11.9	1.2	
Total	25.9	31.1	27.5	3.6	10.8	1.0	

** significant at 5% level

Table 5: Frequency of visit to the study centre, 2023

Sno.	Variable	Frequency of Visit to study centre			Chi-Sq	r Value
1	Sex	1-2	3-4	5+	4.425	0.034
	Male	56.5	33.8	9.7		
	Female	58.4	24.7	16.9		
2	Employment Status				6.737	-0.009
	Salaried	53.0	33.5	13.4		
	Unemployed	80.0	20.0	0.0		
	Student	66.7	24.4	8.9		
	others	50.0	37.0	13.0		
3	Marital status				6.672	0.085
	Married	53.3	34.1	12.6		
	Single	61.9	28.1	10.0		
	Others	30.0	40.0	30.0		
4	Age (Years)				3.761	0.046
	0-32	62.6	24.2	13.1		
	33-42	54.5	35.7	9.8		
	43+	54.3	33.0	12.8		
	Total (%)	57.0	31.1	11.8		

Visits to the Study Centre by Distance

It is well known that distance of residence of learner and frequency of visiting study for counselling or other purpose has negative association significantly. Respondent has asked “how often visit study centre” and “what is the distance of Study centre”, they have always visited or attended all the counselling session conducted by study centre those were living within 5 km from their residence as compared to residing more than 5 km.

Table 54 further shows that learners never visited study those were living more than 50 km, most of them have visited living within 6 to 20 km of study centre as compared to those living more than 20 km from their study centre, sometime visited those living 21-50 km, but none of them were often visited. It indicates that distance and visiting of study were negatively associated significantly with Chi-square value 47.215, which indicates the difference between observed value and expected value.

Table 6: Association between distance of study centre and socio-economic status of the learners

SN.	Variable	Distance between residence to study centre					Chi-Sq	r	
1	Sex	<5	6-10	11-20	21-50	>50	Total (N)	8.292*	0.042
	Male	15.3	20.8	23.1	15.3	25.5	216		
	Female	16.9	15.7	25.8	5.6	36.0	89		
	Total (%)	15.7	19.3	23.9	12.5	28.5	305		
2	Employment Status							15.121	-0.007
	Salaried	18.9	18.3	19.5	13.4	29.9	164		
	Unemployed	0.0	0.0	20.0	0.0	80.0	5		
	Student	14.4	21.1	26.7	11.1	26.7	90		
	others	8.7	21.7	34.8	13.0	21.7	46		
Total (%)	15.7	19.3	23.9	12.5	28.5	305			
3	Marital status							15.472*	-0.118
	Married	14.1	13.3	27.4	11.9	33.3	135		
	Single	15.6	23.8	22.5	13.8	24.4	160		
	Others	40.0	30.0	0.0	0.0	30.0	10		
Total (%)	15.7	19.3	23.9	12.5	28.5	305			
4	Age (Years)							5.12	0.03
	0-32	17.2	21.2	22.2	12.1	27.3	99		
	33-42	13.4	17.0	28.6	15.2	25.9	112		
	43+	17.0	20.2	20.2	9.6	33.0	94		
Total (%)	15.7	19.3	23.9	12.5	28.5	305			

Note: *Significance @10% level of Chi-Square

Table 5 clearly shows the association between socio-economic status and frequency of visit the study centre for the academic purposes across the regional

centre in India. More than half of the learner both male and female, salaried, married all the age group categories have visited at least 1 to 2 times to their study centre for academic purposes. Table 6 also shows the association between distance of study centre and socio-economic status of the learners. It has found that learners those were living more than 50 km from the study centre have registered more than living in below 5 km from their study centre. It indicates that most of the ODL learners were migrants and living in the cities for the academic purpose. ODL learners were not necessary that they have living in the city for ODL programme, they may be living for their competitive exams or doing another degree in the traditional university. Perception of the learners have discussed in the forthcoming chapter.

Knowledge level of respondent/learners about the evaluation and assessment in ODL

Table7: Knowledge level among the learners about the evaluation methods in ODL

S. No.	Statement for knowledge about the evaluation in ODL	Assignment Mandatory	Paper Pen exam mandatory	Project Work	All	Agree	Don't Know
1	Internal Evaluation	44.9	16.1	3.3	20.3	11.5	3.9
2	External Evaluation	24.3	31.1	5.9	21.3	12.5	4.9
3	ODL evaluation consist only internal	35.1	15.4	4.6	24.3	10.5	10.2
4	Evaluation matrix/rubric is base of ODL	15.7	23.6	4.3	25.6	23.0	7.9
5	NEP 2020 promote ODL system of education	20.7	16.7	4.3	20.0	29.5	8.9

Respondents have asked about the internal and external evaluation and other methods of evaluation. Objective of this question was to know about the internal and external evaluation. Respondent were asked what is important in assignment mandatory, paper pen exam mandatory, project work, whether they are agree with all the statements for ODL, and other. Some of the statements' response is not suitable we want to know whether learners are aware about these statement and components of evaluation. For assignment is mandatory for internal evaluation and paper pen exam is mandatory for external evaluation, project work is compulsory for the PG programme, etc. figures in Table 7 clearly indicates that learners were not aware completely about the what are the components for internal and external evaluation, some of them have reported that assignment is mandatory both internal and external evaluation, 16.1 percent of them were positively responded that paper pen exam is mandatory for internal evaluation which is not correct. About one fifth of them have responded that all five statements are related to all evaluation methods. They have asked whether NEP 2020 is promoting ODL only 29.5 percent of them were agree and nearly 9 percent of them don't know and rest of them were not clear about the NEP 2020. It indicates that maximum number of learners was aware about the ODL and its

components and few of them were not sure about the statement whether right or wrong and they have avoided responding.

Table8: Awareness level of learners about the Open and Distance Learning, 2023

1	ODL Institute is Conducting counseling in	Percent
	F2F Teaching	9.9
	Online	57.5
	Blended	24.7
	Don't know	7.9
2	Which type of University IGNOU is?	
	ODL	67.8
	Both	32.2
3	ODL System of education is easier than traditional system of education	
	No	18.2
	Yes	81.1
	Other	.7
4	Is ODL degree linked with UGC?	
	Yes	90.3
	No	9.7
5	Do you consider ODL as secondary level of education?]	
	No	23.6
	Yes	76.4
6	Do you know about the online education?]	
	No	4.3
	Yes	95.7
7	Have you heard about the MOOCs and its nature?]	
	No	35.3
	Yes	64.7
	Total	305

Awareness level of learners about the ODL Institutes and Distance Education

It is general perception that ODL institute degree is not valid for the government jobs and it is not useful for promotion or career development. This perception is generated because of lack of proper knowledge of ODL mode of education, purpose of open and distance education, main objective of ODL institute, eligibility criteria for enrolment and obtaining degree from ODL institute, they are following proxy information from those who are doing any degree from the traditional university and their perception is negative towards ODL university. Respondents those were learner in any ODL

institute have asked few general perceptual questions to know their understanding about the ODL. Table 8 shows that about 8 percent of the learners were not known whether ODL institute is conducting any counselling for the students. More than half of them has responded that ODL institute is conducting counselling online followed by blended mode and close to 10 percent of them responded face to face teaching (F2F). It indicates that they have not read programme guide properly or they have not access student support services on time.

They have asked about the status of IGNOU on “which type of University IGNOU is?” and interestingly nearly one third (32.2%) of them have responded that IGNOU is providing both open and traditional university, although in open word clearly mentioned in Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU). They have further asked whether ODL mode education is easier than traditional system of education, and vast majority (81.1%) of them have responded positively. There were 90.3 percent of them opined that ODL degree is linked with University Grants Commission (UGC). Slightly more three fourths (76.4%) of the respondents have considered ODL system education is secondary level or inferior degree than traditional university.

The online education, which flexible and available any time for the students. Almost all the respondents (95.7%) knew

online education. There were 65 percent of them have heard about the MOOCs and its nature.

In this chapter we have discussed about the awareness and knowledge level of the respondents about the ODL mode of education and it's all the components. Awareness and knowledge affect perception and change the attitudes, and change the perception towards ODL institute.

Conclusion

According to Psychologist Freud, there are three levels of awareness in human consciousness. Almost all the learners were aware and fully aware about the ODL and its components. Interesting to note here that none of the respondents have responded that they were not aware about the ODL mode of education, many of them were not aware about all components of ODL mode of education. It indicates that fully awareness comes after using of the system of ODL. Self-Learning Materials (SLMs) are base of ODL. The course materials are significant inputs of learning in distance education system. Usually in the Indian context they are understood as print-based self-study materials. As a student of ODLs you have noticed that the study materials are classified into different areas of study in the form of Blocks and Units. About 8 percent of the learners were not known whether ODL institute is conducting any counselling for the students. More than half

of them has responded that ODL institute is conducting counselling online followed by blended mode and close to 10 percent of them responded face to face teaching (F2F). It indicates that they have not read programme guide properly or they have not access student support services on time.

Learning the Indigenous System of Knowledge is considered the essential and inseparable part of entire education. In this concern the entire system is a supporting study to explore the learning components as well as to enhance the learner's capacity and competence. The each and every age group, social conditions play important role for healthy and effecting learning which will be helpful to mitigate the purpose of education.

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